

УДК 334.78

*Eleonora Tsybulska, Kateryna Velychko, Kateryna Ovcharenko***TRANSFORMATION OF BUSINESS MODELS
OF ENTITIES OF ECONOMIC RELATIONS
IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY**

The article is devoted to the transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations in the digital economy. It was illustrated that the transformation of socio-economic systems in the direction of the development of the digital form of manifestation of economic relations is an urgent problem that requires the close attention of researchers and practitioners. The modern dynamically developing environment poses new challenges to subjects of economic relations. The development of technology, automation, and repeated acceleration of processes taking place in the external environment create the need to change traditional approaches to the formation of business models of conducting business. Key aspects of the transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations in the digital economy were considered in the study. The importance of the influence of the conditions of digitalization of the economy on the process of forming a business model of a business structure was emphasized. Comparative characteristics of the traditional and platform business models of the subject of economic relations were regarded. Classification of forms of implementation of business models in conditions of digitization of the economy was presented. It was stated in the article that the digital transformation of the system of economic relations of the business structure presupposes the necessity of a fundamental restructuring of its classical business model. It was concluded that the digital transformation of the business model can be considered a form of conducting business that involves the active implementation of digital technologies in the process of forming the value chain. It was also shown that the application of platform business models rapidly replaces competition between subjects of economic relations with competition between business platforms, leaving only narrow market niches for traditional business models. The study demonstrated that the transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations to the conditions of digitalization of the economy facilitates and accelerates their business processes, makes their work more efficient, and allows increasing market capitalization of business structures.

Keywords: transformation, business model, subject of economic relations, digital economy, traditional business model, platform (digital) business model, market capitalization.

Цибульська Е. І., Величко К. Ю., Овчаренко К. В. Трансформація бізнес-моделей суб'єктів економічних відносин в цифровій економіці

Стаття присвячена трансформації бізнес-моделей суб'єктів економічних відносин в цифровій економіці. Показано, що трансформація соціально-економічних систем у напрямі розвитку цифрової форми прояву економічних відносин є актуальною проблемою, яка потребує пильної уваги дослідників та практичних працівників. Сучасне середовище, що динамічно розвивається, ставить перед суб'єктами економічних відносин нові виклики. Розвиток технологій, автоматизація та багаторазове прискорення процесів, що відбуваються у зовнішньому середовищі, створюють необхідність зміни традиційних підходів до формування бізнес-моделей ведення бізнесу. У роботі розглядаються ключові аспекти трансформації бізнес-моделей суб'єктів економічних відносин в цифровій економіці. Наголошується на важливості впливу умов цифровізації економіки на процес формування бізнес-моделі бізнес-структури. Надається порівняльна характеристика традиційної та платформенної бізнес-моделі суб'єкта економічних відносин. Представлена класифікація форм реалізації бізнес-моделей в умовах цифровізації економіки. Цифрова трансформація системи економічних відношень бізнес-структури передбачає необхідність докорінної перебудови її класичної бізнес-моделі. Зроблено висновок щодо того, що цифрову трансформацію бізнес-моделі можливо розглядати як форму ведення бізнесу, що передбачає активну імплементацію цифрових технологій у процесі формування ланцюжка створення вартості. Показано, що застосування платформених бізнес-моделей стрімко заміняє конкуренцію між суб'єктами економічних відносин на конкуренцією між бізнес-платформами, залишаючи для традиційної бізнес-моделі лише вузькі ринкові ніші. Трансформація бізнес-моделей суб'єктів економічних відносин до умов цифровізації економіки полегшує та прискорює їх бізнес-процеси, робить їх роботу більш ефективною та дозволяє підвищити ринкову капіталізацію бізнес-структур.

Ключові слова: трансформація, бізнес-модель, суб'єкт економічних відносин, цифрова економіка, традиційна бізнес-модель, платформенна (цифрова) бізнес-модель, ринкова капіталізація.

Formulation of the problem. The world economy is undergoing significant changes related to digital technologies. Digitization is one of the main trends in the development of the modern economy. The availability

of modern technologies: digital platforms, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, Internet of Things technology, big data, and blockchain – radically changes the possibilities of using the information in business to optimize the processes of increasing productivity and improving the quality of goods and services. Increasing the competitiveness of business structures is currently impossible without digital transformation. And this, in turn, requires business structures to fundamentally rebuild and adapt their business models to the challenges of the digital economy. Transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations facilitates and speeds up business processes, makes them more efficient, and allows for attracting more customers, making economic subjects more competitive. Herewith, the competitiveness of the business structure is one of the key factors of its success and stability in the market, which makes the research topic relevant.

Analysis of publications on the research topic. Ideas about the direction of digital transformation of the economy began to shape in the mid-90s of the 20th century. K. Kurokawa, T. Umesao, Y. Hayashi, E. Masuda, M. Castells, and J. Naisbit made a significant contribution to the understanding of the role of ICT in the development of society and the conditions of digitalization of the economy. Currently, A. Bryan, K. Kelly, N. Negroponte, D. Westerman, and others are dealing with the problems of the digital transformation of the economy. On the topic of digital transformation of business, there are few scientific works performed by consulting companies [1–4].

The concept of a business model first appeared in scientific works at the end of the 1940s. Until the second half of the 1990s, it was considered mainly in the context of corporate strategy and was primarily associated with the works of M. Porter and P. Drucker, although they did not directly use this term.

The modern concept of the business model was first presented by H. Hemel and K. Prahalad. From the point of view of the mentioned authors, the business model is perceived as a connecting link between the company's strategy and the business processes implemented by it [5]. The most famous business model today is the model of the Swiss business analysts O. Osterwald and I. Pinye – Business Model Canvas [6], within which

the authors identified two groups of main factors that form value and ensure the competitiveness of the modern business structure. The first “input” group refers to suppliers and includes resources, partners, and processes. The second group (conventionally “outgoing”) defines customers: target groups of consumers, distribution channels, and customer interaction technologies. The Business Model Canvas also includes two groups of the most important financial indicators of a business structure’s activity, namely cost structure and income streams, which largely determine its competitiveness.

The development of the views of scientists on the formation of the traditional (classical) business model of the company was presented in the works of J. Linder and S. Cantrell [7], G. Chesbrough [8], Roseia M. and Wertner H. [9]. Despite the fairly large number of works devoted to the classical business model of the functioning of companies, there is a huge gap regarding the features of the transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations in the digital economy, the main features of digital business models have not been studied much, and the impact of digital technologies on the size of the market capitalization of business structures requires further study.

The purpose of the research is to consider the peculiarities of the transformation of business models of business entities in the digital economy, to highlight the main features of digital business models, and to investigate the impact of digital technologies on the size of the market capitalization of business structures.

Main results of the research. The modern business model should fit into the concept of the digital economy, which can be presented as a space of information technologies that interact with each other [10, c. 238].

Let’s consider the features of the transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations in the digital economy (Figure 1).

Digitization of the economy leads to a significant development of business based on computer and information technologies and accordingly to the transformation of its business model. In the conditions of the digital transformation of the economy, business is gradually moving from the real material economy to the Internet. In this regard, the costs of conducting

Figure 3 – Peculiarities of the transformation of business models of economic entities in the conditions of digitalization of the economy
Compiled by the authors based on [11 –15]

business are reduced for companies, and the business pays only for access to the Internet. As a result, computer network platforms have become the most important resource of modern business that conducts operations on the Internet. Individual companies create them for themselves, but many use already existing platforms in the cloud technology system, which allows them to significantly save the capital necessary to create and operate a network or communication business.

At the same time, analyzing the direction of changes in the essential content of business models in the digital economy, some researchers, in contrast to traditional models, form the concept of a digital or platform business model, within which the formation of value for the client is carried out based on the use of information and communication technologies, which provide the possibility of interaction of economic subjects in real time [16].

A comparative analysis of traditional and digital business models of business entities is presented in Figure 2.

The company's digital business models are based on a common base platform, which makes it possible to reduce the transaction costs of interaction between participants in market relations due to the sharp acceleration of communications and the elimination of intermediaries. Bright examples of digital (platform) business models that have changed traditional business models are, in our opinion, Uber's driver call service and Airbnb's apartment reservation service. Both the new (platform) and the old (traditional) business models are aimed at satisfying one need – moving the client from one point to another with minimal time spent on ordering and performing the service, payment, receiving feedback (optionally), and with minimal prices for the service. The traditional business model for creating value used the link between the customer – the taxi customer, and the person who directly provides the service – the taxi driver. This link was a call center that received and processed orders and feedback (mostly negative). The platform business model eliminated the middle link – the call center, and replaced it with a new, more efficient tool – a mobile application, which allowed to reduce time and financial costs, adding value to all participants of this relationship.

It is necessary to highlight the criteria for comparing platform and

Figure 2 – A comparative analysis of traditional and digital business models of business entity

Compiled by the authors based on [10,16]

traditional business models. The following can be considered as the main criteria for selecting platform business models:

- 1) temporary criterion: direct (without intermediaries-agents) interaction of participants in market relations in real-time;
- 2) financial criterion: low transaction costs of platform user interaction;
- 3) spatial criterion: absence of entry barriers to the system [16, c. 88].

As for the criterion of the company's costs for entering the business, it can be noted that in the traditional business model, the use of a link that ensures interaction between participants in economic relations is initially laid down. At the same time, creating a platform requires high development costs, but the benefits of its use are expected to compensate for the initial investment. It was noted that the creation of a platform requires both financial resources and a certain initial level of trust of potential participants in each other, as well as in the creator of the business platform.

Digital business models make it possible to reorient the company's activities to a broader level, compete in global markets, attract new resources for the production of goods or services, and earn a large profit.

Given the growing role of e-commerce in today's economy, there is a need to separate and classify digital business models related to Internet sales. P. Timmers proposed his version of a similar classification, singling out the following forms of digital business models [17]: online stores; Internet integrators; online auctions; internet services; information intermediaries; collaborative platforms; trust models.

A more detailed taxonomy of business models that have spread in the digital environment was proposed by M. Rappa, who believes that the development of the Internet can become a catalyst for the emergence of new forms of these models. The following are the main categories of business models on the Internet by M. Rappa [18]:

- brokerage business models: market exchange model, buy-sell model, purchase request collection model, auction brokerage model, transactional brokerage model, distributor model, search agent model, virtual market model;
- advertising business models: the portal model;
- business models of information mediation: the model of advertising networks, model of audience research, model of stimulating marketing, model of meta mediation;
- business models of wholesale and retail trade: e-seller model, e-catalog model;
- business models of direct marketing: use by direct producers of Internet forms of organization of interaction with buyers;

- business models of partner relations: the model of banner exchange, other models of payment for access to information on the Internet;
- community business models: open source model, open content model, social networks;
- subscription business models: content service model, other models of providing subscription information.

Let’s consider the impact of digital technologies on the size of the market capitalization of companies. The ratings of the top 1000 leading companies in the world for the years 2019–2022 served as the source of information for the study. The results of the study are presented in Table 1 and show that the first five places in the top 1000 ranking according to the criterion of market capitalization during the years 2019–2022 are owned not by material production companies, but by network business companies that are engaged only in mediation in the exchange of information, that is, info mediation. These companies have successfully transformed and flexibly adapted their business models to the challenges of digitalization.

Table 1 – Top 5 companies by market capitalization for 2019–2022, billion \$

№	Years							
	2019		2020		2021		2022	
	Company	Capita- lization	Company	Capita- lization	Company	Capita- lization	Company	Capita- lization
1	Apple	1153	Apple	1323	Apple	2256	Apple	2825
2	Microsoft	1101	Microsoft	1215	Microsoft	1682	Microsoft	2358
3	Alphabet	902	Alphabet	944	Amazon	1634	Alphabet	1820
4	Amazon	887	Amazon	941	Alphabet	1185	Amazon	1649
5	Facebook	543	Facebook	598	Facebook	778	Meta Platforms (Facebook)	923

Compiled by the authors based on [19]

The analysis of the data in Table 1 shows that during the years 2019–2022 Apple is the world leader in terms of market capitalization, Microsoft is in second place and Alphabet and Amazon alternate in different years in

places 3 and 4. Facebook (Meta Platforms) occupies fifth place with enviable constancy.

Apple, Microsoft, Alphabet, Amazon, and Meta Platforms (Facebook) are the flagships of digitization. These companies started the digital transformation of their business among the first. The given ratings of the five leading companies in the world and the size of their market capitalization allow for assuming a close connection between a company's effective digital business model and its level of competitiveness. This relationship confirms the fact that the more effectively a company has digitally transformed its business and created a flexible platform business model, the higher its market capitalization is. This is characteristic of companies engaged in information media.

Conclusions. Digital transformation of the business structure requires a fundamental restructuring of its classic business model. The digital transformation of the business model can be considered a form of doing business, which involves the active implementation of digital technologies in the process of forming the value chain. The application of digital (platform) business models is rapidly replacing the competition between the subjects of economic relations with the competition between business platforms, leaving only narrow market niches for the traditional business model. The transformation of business models of subjects of economic relations to the conditions of digitalization of the economy facilitates and accelerates their business processes, makes their work more efficient, and allows to increase market capitalization of business structures.

Список бібліографічних посилань

1. Collins, L., Fineman, D. and Tsuchida, A. (2017). *Human Capital Trends 2017 Deloitte Global*. Deloitte [online]. Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/human-capital/articles/introduction-human-capital-trends.html> [Accessed 21 November 2023].
2. Geissbauer, R. et al. (2020). Digital factories 2020-shaping the future of manufacturing. [online] In: *Pwc.de*. Available at: <https://www.pwc.de/de/digitale-transformation/digital-factories-2020-shaping-the-future-of-manufacturing.pdf> [Accessed 21 November 2023].
3. Strack, R. et al. (2017). How to Gain and Develop Digital Talent and Skills. [online]. In: *Bcg.com*. Available at: <https://www.bcg.com/de-de/publications/2017/>

people-organization-technology-how-gain-develop-digital-talent-skills.aspx. [Accessed 21 November 2023].

4. Ziegler, M., Rossmann, S. (2017). Digital Machinery Decoded. A practical guide for machinery companies to navigate digital transformation and outperform competition. [online] In: *Porsche*. Available at: https://www.porsche-consulting.com/fileadmin/docs/Startseite/News/tt1309/Porsche_Consulting_Digital_Machinery_Decoded.pdf. [Accessed 21 November 2023].

5. Hamel, G., Prahalad, C. (1996). *Competing for the Future*. Boston : Harvard Business Review Press, 384 p.

6. Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y. and Tucci. C. r L. (2005). Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept. In: *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 1, pp.128–146.

7. Linder, J., Cantrell, S. (2000). *Changing Business Models Surveying the Landscape. PhD Thesis*. Accenture Institute for Strategic Change, Cambridge, 120p.

8. Chesbrough, H. (2006). *Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology*. Boston: Harvard Business Press, 168 p.

9. Rozeia, M., Werthner, H. (2011). Business Models and Business Strategy – Phenomenon of Explicitnes. In: *International Journal of Global Business & Competitiveness*, 1, p. 15–32.

10. Tkachenko E.A., Khuazhev A.A. (2021). Transformation of business models of entrepreneurial structures in the conditions of digitalization. In: *Economics: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow*, 11 (4A), pp. 235–244.

11. Гринько, П.Л. (2020). Цифрова трансформація бізнесу в умовах розвитку інноваційних процесів в Україні. В : *Бізнес Інформ*, 3. С. 53–58.

12. Коляденко, С.В. (2016). Цифрова економіка: передумови та етапи становлення в Україні і у світі. В: *Економіка. Фінанси. Менеджмент: актуальні питання науки і практики*, 6, С. 106–107.

13. Ляшенко, В.І., Вишневський, О.С. (2018). *Цифрова модернізація економіки України як можливість проривного розвитку*. Київ: НАН України, Ін-т економіки пром-сті, 252 с.

14. Пугачевська К.Й., Пугачевська К.С. (2018). Цифровізація економіки як фактор підвищення конкурентоспроможності країни. В: *Інфраструктура ринку*, 25, С. 39–45.

15. Устенко, М., Руських, А. (2019). Діджиталізація: основа конкурентоспроможності підприємства в реаліях цифрової економіки. *Вісник економіки транспорту і промисловості*, 68, С. 181–192.

16. Garifullin, V.M., Zyabrikov, V.V. (2019). Types of business models of

companies in the digital economy. In: *Journal of Creative Economy*, 13. (1). P. 83–92.

17. Timmers, P. (1998). Business models for electronic markets. In: *Electronic Markets*, 2, P. 5–15.

18. Rappa, M. Business Models on The Web. Available at: <http://digitalenterprise.org/models/models.html>. [Accessed 21 November 2023].

19. VALUE-TODAY [online]. Available at: <https://www.value.today/world-top-1000-companies-as-on-dec-25-2022> [Accessed 23 March 2023].

References

1. Collins, L., Fineman, D. and Tsuchida, A. (2017). *Human Capital Trends 2017 Deloitte Global*. Deloitte [online]. Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/pages/human-capital/articles/introduction-human-capital-trends.html> [Accessed 21 November 2023].

2. Geissbauer, R. et al. (2020). Digital factories 2020-shaping the future of manufacturing [online]. In: *Pwc.de*. Available at: <https://www.pwc.de/de/digitale-transformation/digital-factories-2020-shaping-the-future-of-manufacturing.pdf> [Accessed 21 November 2023].

3. Strack, R. et al. (2017). How to Gain and Develop Digital Talent and Skills. [online]. In: *Bcg.com*. Available at: <https://www.bcg.com/de-de/publications/2017/people-organization-technology-how-gain-develop-digital-talent-skills.aspx> [Accessed 21 November 2023].

4. Ziegler, M., Rossmann, S. (2017). Digital Machinery Decoded. A practical guide for machinery companies to navigate digital transformation and outperform competition [online]. In: *Porsche*. Available at: https://www.porsche-consulting.com/fileadmin/docs/Startseite/News/tt1309/Porsche_Consulting_Digital_Machinery_Decoded.pdf. [Accessed 21 November 2023].

5. Hamel, G., Prahalad, C. (1996). *Competing for the Future*. Boston : Harvard Business Review Press, 384 p.

6. Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y. and Tucci, C. (2005). Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept. In: *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 1, pp.128–146.

7. Linder, J., Cantrell, S. (2000). Changing Business Models Surveying the Landscape. PhD Thesis, Accenture Institute for Strategic Change, Cambridge, 120 p.

8. Chesbrough, H. (2006). *Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology*. Harvard Business Press, 168 p.

9. Rozeia, M., Werthner, H. (2011). *Business Models and Business Strategy* –

Phenomenon of Explicitnes. In: *International Journal of Global Business & Competitiveness*, 1, p. 15–32.

10. Tkachenko E. A., Khuazhev A. A. (2021). Transformation of business models of entrepreneurial structures in the conditions of digitalization. In: *Economics: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow*, 11 (4A), pp. 235–244.

11. Hrynko, P.L. (2020). Tsyfrova transformatsiia biznesu v umovakh rozvytku innovatsiinykh protsesiv v Ukraini [Digital transformation of business in the minds of the development of innovative processes in Ukraine]. In: *Biznes Inform* [Business Inform], 3, P. 53–58.

12. Koliadenko, S.V. (2016). Tsyfrova ekonomika: peredumovy ta etapy stanovlennia v Ukraini i u sviti [Digital economy: rethinking the stages of development in Ukraine and in the world]. In: *Ekonomika. Finansy. Menedzhment: aktualni pytannia nauky i praktyky* [Economy. Finance. Management: current nutrition of science and practice], 6, P. 106–107.

13. Liashenko, V.I., Vyshnevskiy, O.S. (2018). *Tsyfrova modernizatsiia ekonomiky Ukrainy yak mozhlyvist proryvnoho rozvytku* [Digital modernization of the economy of Ukraine as the possibility of a breakthrough development]. Kyiv: NAN Ukrainy, In-t ekonomiky prom-sti, 252 p.

14. Puhachevska K. Y., Puhachevska K.S. (2018). Tsyfrovizatsiia ekonomiky yak faktor pidvyshchennia konkurentospromozhnosti krainy [Digitization of the economy as a factor in promoting the competitiveness of the country]. In: *Infrastruktura rynku* [Market infrastructure], 25, P. 39–45.

15. Ustenko, M., Ruskykh, A. (2019). Didzhytalizatsiia: osnova konkurentospromozhnosti pidpriemstva v realiiakh tsyfrovoy ekonomiky [Digitization: the basis of enterprise competitiveness in the realities of the digital economy]. In: *Visnyk ekonomiky transportu i promyslovosti* [Herald of the economy of transport and industry], 68, P. 181–192.

16. Garifullin, B.M., Zyabrikov, V.V. (2019). Types of business models of companies in the digital economy. In: *Journal of Creative Economy*, 13. (1). P. 83–92.

17. Timmers, P. (1998). Business models for electronic markets. In: *Electronic Markets*, 2, P. 5–15.

18. Rappa, M. Business Models On The Web [online]. Available at: <http://digitalenterprise.org/models/models.html>. [Accessed 21 November 2023].

19. VALUE-TODAY [online]. Available at: <https://www.value.today/world-top-1000-companies-as-on-dec-25-2022> [Accessed 23 March 2023].